

TAI MUONG NUMERALS

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Abstract

The ten recordings published here introduce Tai Muong numerals from 1 to 150 as well as those for 100, 1000, 10000, 100000, 1000000, as elicited from a female speaker living in Châu Phong Commune (Quỳ Châu District, Nghệ An Province, Vietnam), Lương Thị Hào. These recordings follow a first set of Tai Muong recordings by Lương Thị Dung, also from Châu Phong Commune, already uploaded to Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7471498>) and a presentation of Tai Muong specifically based on the variety spoken by Lương Thị Dung (<https://zenodo.org/record/7472112>).

Tai Muong belongs to a group of Tai varieties spoken in Western Nghệ An, some being referred to as Tai Yo or Tai Pao, which are characterized by a Northern Tai substratum. However Northern Tai numerals, such as those used in Saek ([nuŋ^{B4}] ‘one’, [rək^{DS1}] ‘six’, [cət^{DS2}] ‘seven’, [pe:t^{DL2}] ‘eight’, [ku:c^{C2}] ‘nine’, [sip^{DS4}] ‘ten’), are not used by the speaker. Her numerals are the Southwestern Tai numerals. The only exception – and it is not related to Northern Tai – is the Vietnamese numeral *một* ‘one’, which she consistently uses instead of [nuŋ^{B1}] ‘one’ (in 1 to 10) and [ʔet^{DS3}] ‘one’ (as the unit after any multiple of ten’).

Keywords: Tai Muong, Tai dialects of Western Nghệ An (Vietnam), numerals
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The speaker for this set of recordings is Lương Thị Hào, a relative of Lương Thị Dung whose recordings were previously downloaded to Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7471498>). Lương Thị Hào lives in Châu Phong Commune (Quỳ Châu District, Nghệ An Province, Vietnam). She calls the Tai dialect she speaks “Tai Muong”, which she spells “Táy Muóng” when writing the name of her language in Quốc ngữ script. The languages she uses in her daily life are Vietnamese and Tai Muong. She can read and write English, but she has to use a translation software in many cases. She says she does not understand Lao and Thai (Siamese). I worked with her online for a first elicitation in July 2022.

Since the elicitation covered many lexical items in addition to the numerals which are discussed here, it is possible to say on the basis of auditory judgment that Lương Thị Hào speaks roughly the same language as Lương Thị Dung. A precise tone diagram taking into account the F0 measurements for each tone in the monosyllabic words recorded by Lương Thị Hào will be created at a later point in order to determine to which extent the tone merger and split patterns of the variety she speaks and the variety spoken by her relative are similar.

Tai Muong numerals as elicited from Lương Thị Hào are the numerals used in Southwestern Tai languages. The only exception concerns the Vietnamese numeral ‘một’, which she consistently uses. ‘Một’, a B2 syllable in Vietnamese, bears the tone of DL4 syllables in other Southwestern Tai languages such as Tai Daeng and its dialects spoken in Vietnam and Laos (e.g. Tai Thaeng, known as Tay Thanh in Vietnam). ‘Một’ is used by the speaker to express both the numeral ‘one’ (as in 1 to 10) – [nuŋ^{B1}] in Southwestern Tai – and the unit after any multiple of ten – [ʔet^{DS3}] in Southwestern Tai.

Below are the transcriptions of the numerals in each of the ten recordings. It will be noted that in the transcriptions that follow we have chosen to retain the etymological length of the monophthongs for DL syllables, although they tend to be pronounced short in Tai Muong (e.g., pɛ:t^{DL2}).

- Numerals 1-10 normal pronunciation: [mo:t^{DL4}], [sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [sa:m^{A1}], [si:^{B1}], [ha:^{C1}], [hok^{DS1}], [cet^{DS2}], [pɛ:t^{DL2}], [kaw^{C2}], [sip^{DS1}].
- Numerals 1-10 slow pronunciation: [mo:t^{DL4}], [sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [sa:m^{A1}], [si:^{B1}], [ha:^{C1}], [hok^{DS1}], [cet^{DS2}], [pɛ:t^{DL2}], [kaw^{C2}], [sip^{DS1}].
- Numerals 11-30: [sip^{DS1} mo:t^{DL4}], [sip^{DS1} sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [sip^{DS1} sa:m^{A1}], [sip^{DS1} si:^{B1}], [sip^{DS1} ha:^{C1}], [sip^{DS1} hok^{DS1}], [sip^{DS1} cet^{DS2}], [sip^{DS1} pɛ:t^{DL2}], [sip^{DS1} kaw^{C2}], [sa:w^{A4}], [sa:w^{A4} mo:t^{DL4}], [sa:w^{A4} sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [sa:w^{A4} sa:m^{A1}], [sa:w^{A4} si:^{B1}], [sa:w^{A4} ha:^{C1}], [sa:w^{A4} hok^{DS1}], [sa:w^{A4} cet^{DS2}], [sa:w^{A4} pɛ:t^{DL2}], [sa:w^{A4} kaw^{C2}], [sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1}].
- Numerals 31-50: [sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} mo:t^{DL4}], [sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} sa:m^{A1}], [sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} si:^{B1}], [sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} ha:^{C1}], [sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} hok^{DS1}], [sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} cet^{DS2}], [sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} pɛ:t^{DL2}], [sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} kaw^{C2}], [si:^{B1} sip^{DS1}], [si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} mo:t^{DL4}], [si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} sa:m^{A1}], [si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} si:^{B1}], [si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} ha:^{C1}], [si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} hok^{DS1}], [si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} cet^{DS2}], [si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} pɛ:t^{DL2}], [si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} kaw^{C2}], [ha:^{C1} sip^{DS1}].
- Numerals 51-60: [ha:^{C1} sip^{DS1} mo:t^{DL4}], [ha:^{C1} sip^{DS1} sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [ha:^{C1} sip^{DS1} sa:m^{A1}], [ha:^{C1} sip^{DS1} si:^{B1}], [ha:^{C1} sip^{DS1} ha:^{C1}], [ha:^{C1} sip^{DS1} hok^{DS1}], [ha:^{C1} sip^{DS1} cet^{DS2}], [ha:^{C1} sip^{DS1} pɛ:t^{DL2}], [ha:^{C1} sip^{DS1} kaw^{C2}], [hok^{DS1} sip^{DS1}].
- Numerals 61-70: [hok^{DS1} sip^{DS1} mo:t^{DL4}], [hok^{DS1} sip^{DS1} sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [hok^{DS1} sip^{DS1} sa:m^{A1}], [hok^{DS1} sip^{DS1} si:^{B1}], [hok^{DS1} sip^{DS1} ha:^{C1}], [hok^{DS1} sip^{DS1} hok^{DS1}], [hok^{DS1} sip^{DS1} cet^{DS2}], [hok^{DS1} sip^{DS1} pɛ:t^{DL2}], [hok^{DS1} sip^{DS1} kaw^{C2}], [cet^{DS2} sip^{DS1}].
- Numerals 71-80: [cet^{DS2} sip^{DS1} mo:t^{DL4}], [cet^{DS2} sip^{DS1} sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [cet^{DS2} sip^{DS1} sa:m^{A1}], [cet^{DS2} sip^{DS1} si:^{B1}], [cet^{DS2} sip^{DS1} ha:^{C1}], [cet^{DS2} sip^{DS1} hok^{DS1}], [cet^{DS2} sip^{DS1} cet^{DS2}], [cet^{DS2} sip^{DS1} pɛ:t^{DL2}], [cet^{DS2} sip^{DS1} kaw^{C2}], [pɛ:t^{DL2} sip^{DS1}].
- Numerals 81-100: [pɛ:t^{DL2} sip^{DS1} mo:t^{DL4}], [pɛ:t^{DL2} sip^{DS1} sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [pɛ:t^{DL2} sip^{DS1} sa:m^{A1}], [pɛ:t^{DL2} sip^{DS1} si:^{B1}], [pɛ:t^{DL2} sip^{DS1} ha:^{C1}], [pɛ:t^{DL2} sip^{DS1} hok^{DS1}], [pɛ:t^{DL2} sip^{DS1} cet^{DS2}], [pɛ:t^{DL2} sip^{DS1} pɛ:t^{DL2}], [pɛ:t^{DL2} sip^{DS1} kaw^{C2}], [kaw^{C2} sip^{DS1}], [kaw^{C2} sip^{DS1} mo:t^{DL4}], [kaw^{C2} sip^{DS1} sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [kaw^{C2} sip^{DS1} sa:m^{A1}], [kaw^{C2} sip^{DS1} si:^{B1}], [kaw^{C2} sip^{DS1} ha:^{C1}], [kaw^{C2} sip^{DS1} hok^{DS1}], [kaw^{C2} sip^{DS1} cet^{DS2}], [kaw^{C2} sip^{DS1} pɛ:t^{DL2}], [kaw^{C2} sip^{DS1} kaw^{C2}], [hɔ:j^{C4}].
- Numerals 101-150: [hɔ:j^{C4} mo:t^{DL4}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:m^{A1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} si:^{B1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} ha:^{C1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} hok^{DS1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} cet^{DS2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} pɛ:t^{DL2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} kaw^{C2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sip^{DS1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sip^{DS1} mo:t^{DL4}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sip^{DS1} sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sip^{DS1} sa:m^{A1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sip^{DS1} si:^{B1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sip^{DS1} ha:^{C1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sip^{DS1} hok^{DS1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sip^{DS1} cet^{DS2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sip^{DS1} pɛ:t^{DL2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sip^{DS1} kaw^{C2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:w^{A4}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:w^{A4} mo:t^{DL4}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:w^{A4} sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:w^{A4} sa:m^{A1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:w^{A4} si:^{B1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:w^{A4} ha:^{C1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:w^{A4} hok^{DS1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:w^{A4} cet^{DS2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:w^{A4} pɛ:t^{DL2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:w^{A4} kaw^{C2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} mo:t^{DL4}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} sa:m^{A1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} si:^{B1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} ha:^{C1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} hok^{DS1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} cet^{DS2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} pɛ:t^{DL2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} sa:m^{A1} sip^{DS1} kaw^{C2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} si:^{B1} sip^{DS1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} mo:t^{DL4}], [hɔ:j^{C4} si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} sɔ:ŋ^{A1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} sa:m^{A1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} si:^{B1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} ha:^{C1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} hok^{DS1}], [hɔ:j^{C4} si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} cet^{DS2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} pɛ:t^{DL2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} si:^{B1} sip^{DS1} kaw^{C2}], [hɔ:j^{C4} ha:^{C1} sip^{DS1}].
- Numerals 100, 1000, 10000, 100000, 1000000: [hɔ:j^{C4}], [pan^{A4}], [sip^{DS1} pan^{A4}], [hɔ:j^{C4} pan^{A4}], [sip^{DS1} hɔ:j^{C4} pan^{A4}].